

Open Research Information Agenda (ORIA)
National PID Graph Pilot
Project Report

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1. Introduction

The Netherlands holds a significant position in the advancement of research infrastructure, attributed to its robust research culture and leadership when it comes to research reforms and the transition to Open Science. In this landscape, the Open Research Information Agenda (ORIA) is a community-driven initiative aimed at safeguarding digital sovereignty and enhancing the quality of reporting, evaluation, and discoverability of Dutch research. It involves representatives from the Dutch Research Council (NWO), Universities of the Netherlands (UNL), and SURF.

The National PID Graph Pilot is one of the multiple pilots under ORIA involving representatives from Delft University of Technology, Eindhoven University of Technology, Erasmus University Rotterdam, University of Groningen, Utrecht University, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, and SURF. The pilot gained insight into the value proposition of a PID graph, the technology requirements of a PID graph, and the quality of information of underlying sources. Additionally, it facilitated a community around open research information.

This report outlines the National PID Graph Pilot working group activities conducted over the course of the pilot. It presents the lessons learned for each of the objectives in the pilot and proposes recommendations for further development.

2. Objectives and Approach

The objectives are derived from the working plan “Een eerste pilot voor een OKB”. We have listed them in table 1 and grouped them according to topic.

The working group has worked iteratively covering each of these topics. Table 1 lists the activities that were conducted for each of the topics. During 2-weekly meetings we discussed the progress on these topics.

Table 1 Overview of topics, objectives and activities

Topic	Objective & Activities
Community	Facilitate a community that builds up knowledge and shares about open research information <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bi-weekly working-group meetings• Two community events• Engagement with international community
Value	Define the value proposition of a PID graph (applicability for use cases from the Business Case) <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Collect user stories from:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ (a) literature

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ (b) pilot partners ○ (c) the community
Technology	<p>Gain experience with the technology of a PID Graph</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Setup PoC environment and explore technologies ● Access and load information from (a) local CRIS instances and (b) international PID graphs and (c) national sources ● Optimize and query the graph for user stories <p>Gain insight into how we can automatically improve the quality of the primary sources based on insights from PID Graph</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Validate user stories
Information	<p>Gain insight into the relationship between a national PID graph and local and international sources (positioning in information architecture)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consider standards and best practices ● Consult with privacy advisor ● Analyse local (Pure-based) CRIS instances ● Access local CRIS information from pilot partners
Quality	<p>Gain insight into quality, completeness and reusability of existing local and/or national and international primary and open data sources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Addressed in a separate study¹</i>
Finances	<p>Gain insight into required finances and control for a national PID graph</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Not addressed during the pilot</i>

3. Community

The project group consisted of 8-10 members from the 6 participating institutes and SURF². The roles of the participants ranged from CRIS administrators to innovation managers and system administrators. The group met bi-weekly for a period of approximately 4 months.

Over the course of the pilot two community events were organized, both focusing on national and international PID graph initiatives. During the first event we gathered user

¹

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1uYtjmgPWeMbTUq6YqOgp78C0SVXUkzLoyWB2_1VZcn0/edit#slide=id.g1c9ca6f74df_0_2191

² Jeffrey Sweeney (EUR), Rik Janssen (Utrecht University), Nick Veenstra (RUG), Maurice Vanderfeesten (VU), Maarten Hoogerwerf (SURF), Petra Dickhaut (TU Eindhoven), Armand Guicherit (TU Delft), Andjela Tomić (TU Delft), Tim Veken (VU), Tung Tung Chan (EUR), Reinout Dam (VU), Max Paulus (VU)

stories and gained information on the information structure and technology. The second event focused on recent results in the pilot and related initiatives.

We also worked towards bridging together initiatives being developed by OpenAIRE, EuroCRIS, and EOSC and consulted with international partners working on similar projects (e.g. research.fi, researchportal.be).

During the meetings and events, we learned that the community is diverse, with different perspectives on the topic and expectations from the project or a PID graph (e.g. as a federated CRIS or as a national subset of the international PID and metadata infrastructures such as ORCID, Datacite, OpenAIRE and OpenAlex). The meetings and events were important to learn about the different perspectives and a start to co-collaborate, co-learn and co-develop (see section 6).

4. Value

To understand the value of a PID Graph, we collected user stories from recent papers (e.g. Aryani et al. “Open Science Graphs must interoperate”³), from the project plan, the partners, and from the community events (see also Appendix A). For more focused discussion, comparison with international partners and better understanding of the value proposition, we grouped them into four categories:

- Improving **visibility** of research outcomes, towards better reuse
- Improving **reporting** on research outcomes, towards better steering and accountability
- Improving **exchange** of research information, towards better quality and lower administrative pressure.
- Improving insight and control over our own research information, towards better **digital sovereignty**

For each of these categories of value we derived simple user stories to illustrate the value and test the technology. From the discussions on these user stories, we learned that the focus should be on cross-institutional user stories, and they should illustrate the advantages of graph technology.

Category	As a	I want to	So that I can
Visibility	Researcher	see researchers that produce output on a topic	I can identify potential partners for a grant proposal
Reporting	Institutional Policymaker	overview of Dutch affiliated institutions that we co-author with	evaluate and improve investments in strategic collaborations

³ Aryani, A., Fenner, M., Manghi, P., Mannocci, A., Stocker, M. (2020). Open Science Graphs Must Interoperate!. In: Bellatreche, L., et al. ADBIS, TPD and EDA 2020 Common Workshops and Doctoral Consortium. TPD ADBIS 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1260. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-55814-7_16

Exchange	CRIS admin	ask for known identifiers (ORCIDs) of our researchers	improve completeness of our RIS and provide better output suggestions to researchers
Sovereignty	Community	add / improve new types of information to our systems	measure impact of new policies

In Appendix H, we demonstrate how the graph can efficiently retrieve an overview of publications that are co-authored by at least TUE and TUD, as a basis for the user story on reporting.

5. Information

We explored standards and best practices from literature, local CRIS instances (Pure), and international portals. We decided to start with a focus on the Research Graph Metamodel as our central (or ‘target’) schema, as this is minimal and vendor independent. The target schema covers the entities Researcher, Organization, Grant, Research Data, and Publication⁴. However, the source systems (Pure-based) use the entities Researcher, Organization, Award, Project, and Result (see Appendix B). Though these schemas are similar, some transformations are needed. As projects are not registered to the same degree across institutions, it was convenient that these are not covered by our target schema. The source schema therefore included the entities Researcher, Organization, Award and Result.

By aggregating data from multiple sources, the PID Graph will have to deal with potentially different versions of the same record. A publication, its PID record, its occurrence in multiple institutional CRIS systems and its records in e.g. OpenAIRE or OpenAlex may have different versions of the truth, e.g. due to different roles, or different methods for enrichment. The quality of one version may be better suited for discoverability, whereas the quality of another version may be better suited for reporting. We must have a good understanding of these roles and methods for the different values and user stories.

Note that other initiatives are investigating better usage of PIDs and metadata standards for these entities (e.g. PID Roadmap, Metadata for Applied Science, and FAIRCORE4EOSC).

5.1 Privacy

In the pilot we agreed to harvest multiple CRIS's from the partners, including information about researchers. From an academic perspective this is public information, and an essential part of scholarly communication. From an institutional perspective this is personal information on (a.o.) employees, that should be treated with care. We want to understand why and how we are allowed to process information about researchers. We scoped this question to the (temporary and non-public) environment of the pilot.

⁴ See <https://researchgraph.org/schema/>

We made an overview of the personal information that we process ("privacy inventarisatie" template from SURF) and the corresponding risks ("pre DPIA" template) and discussed this with a privacy advisor of SURF. We learned the following:

- Personal information is processed, but with limited sensitivity. We consider the legal basis to be "legitimate interest"⁵ as we provide insight into (publicly) financed knowledge and research, on behalf of our members, and contribute to the public trust in research.
- We should be prepared to respond to requests from subjects for their right for insight, correction, deletion, etc. Within the pilot, we can process these manually.
- We discussed that the following reasons for requiring a DPIA do not play a big (enough) role: *Big data processing*, *Connected databases* and the application of *New technologies* (RDF, Graph technology).

In consultation with the privacy advisor of SURF we decided to proceed, and the pilot partners authorized the pilot to harvest the information from their CRIS's (for the closed pilot environment, for the duration of the pilot).

Beyond the pilot, we need experts on research information, law, and privacy to investigate this and perform a collaborative DPIA, so that all institutions understand how valuable information about researchers can be shared and added to a national PID Graph. Note that we learned from discussions with colleagues in Finland and Poland that they needed to change their law.

6. Technology

This section describes the various technologies explored during the pilot and how they relate to the community, the value and the information.

6.1 Development and Setup

Four technologies were chosen for further examination: 1) Neo4j Community, 2) Research in Context (Ric) Graph, 3) VIVO, and 4) Research Graph⁶. After determining that the available code base for Research Graph is not recently updated, we excluded it from further consideration. The other three were installed on a central staging environment hosted in the SURF Research Cloud.

The central staging environment provided a secure, modular, and reconfigurable workspace to develop a proof-of-concept architecture. The central staging environment allows for future data-sharing/enrichment opportunities with other ORIA pilot projects and/or other national, European, and international initiatives.

⁵ See all 6 options for legal basis at: <https://gdpr-text.com/read/article-6/>

⁶ <https://researchgraph.org/>

System requirements and software configurations were iteratively co-adapted to meet the guiding principles outlined in the Open Research Information Agenda⁷.

A RicGraph⁸ instance was configured to harvest OpenAlex and Research Software Directory information for the five participating universities as well as national-level research information from organizations such as NWO and DANS (see Appendix D).

A separate VIVO instance was configured to ingest ROR and ORCID information for the five participating Universities. This installation provides multi-user self-service capabilities for researchers to view and manage research information⁹ (see Appendix C).

Source Pure data from the five participating Universities was aggregated within a separate Neo4j Community graph database installation based on concept source and target schemas identified within the initial search process (see Appendix B).

Example use cases from this configuration were presented to the PID working group during a community event to stimulate discussion on use cases. Use cases were organized into categories within a preliminary development roadmap (see Appendix A).

The Neo4j Community configuration containing Pure data was further optimized for performance, functionality, and reliability. This optimization led to the creation of the proof-of-concept National PID Graph Architecture (see Appendix G).

The Neo4j Community *Awesome Procedures on Cypher*¹⁰ (APOC) library provides a rich library of graph operations¹¹ to fulfill automated use cases. For instance, referential integrity maintained in the proof-of-concept National PID Graph Architecture allows for generation of virtual¹² nodes and relationships to filter properties, visualize patterns, identify duplicate records, compare subgraphs across organizations, generate aggregations within hierarchical structures, combine subgraphs, and distill new properties, measures, and relationships.

Dynamic PID ingestion functionality developed during the pilot would allow for rapid generation of customizable graphs and sub-graph derivatives (see Appendix E for several examples of subgraph visualization). Performance tests of native Neo4j imports and exports show low system resource usage and high performance thus providing an advantage against larger graph installations - which are unable to rapidly update and reindex. This presents an opportunity to fill the gap for a 'meso-level' research information system that out functions

⁷ Bijsterbosch, M., Dunning, A., Jansen, D., Haring, M., de Rijcke, S., & Vanderfeesten, M. (2022). Seven Guiding Principles for Open Research Information (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6074944>

⁸ Janssen, R. D. T. (2023). Ricgraph - Research in context graph (v1.11). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10083972>

⁹ VIVO is a general purpose web-based ontology and instance editor with customizable public browsing. With VIVO, researchers can edit their personal research information conforming to ontological constraints. Within the scope of the National PID graph pilot, we installed a VIVO instance and loaded it with relevant ORCID and ROR data using the generate2vivo extensible data ingestion tool.

¹⁰ <https://neo4j.com/labs/apoc/>

¹¹ <https://neo4j.com/docs/apoc/current/>

¹² <https://neo4j.com/labs/apoc/4.1/virtual/>

‘micro-level’ systems held within individual institutions and outperforms ‘macro-level’ European systems.

6.2 National-Level Use Cases

The main value of a National PID Graph is that it enables national-level research information reporting, analysis, and evaluation capabilities that are not possible with alternative approaches. Second, the proof-of-concept architecture adheres to ORIA principles thus providing academic sovereignty. Third, it provides a socio-technical ‘sandbox’ within which national research organizations and participating universities can continue to co-collaborate, co-learn and co-develop learning capabilities. Figures 1-8 show summary information and example subgraphs to facilitate national-level use cases.

6.3 National Reporting, Analysis, Assessment, Evaluation, and Dissemination Capabilities

With further aggregation of CRIS data from all Dutch Universities, the proof-of-concept National PID Graph Architecture would supporting the National PID Graph Roadmap’s proposed developmental phases of Integration, Curation, Generation, and Discovery¹³ aligning with use cases derived from the Open Research Information Agenda.

6.4 Academic Sovereignty and ORIA Adherence

The proof-of-concept National PID Graph Architecture is compliant with ORIA principles. The Neo4j Community graph database engine is free for community use under a GPL v3 license¹⁴. RicGraph functionality is available for use under an MIT license with copyrights reserved by the author¹⁵. VIVO functionality is available for use under a BSD 3-Clause license with copyrights reserved.¹⁶ This means that all software components installed on the central staging environment may be used, modified, and redistributed. This provides a low cost and modular approach to achieving academic sovereignty.

The proof-of-concept architecture provides an autonomous view of aggregated Pure CRIS data thus providing new possibilities in maintaining provenance, transparency, and endurance. The proof-of-concept architecture may therefore be used to interconnect third party and open research information systems as an open information exchange and archiving service.

One constraint in scaling up the proof-of-concept is to develop human expertise in how to further develop the system. Expertise is needed in Cypher Query Language (CQL),¹⁷ for which online training is available.¹⁸ Costs to further develop and validate the proof-of-concept architecture therefore lie mainly in labor costs to develop and maintain customized

¹³ These ‘higher-order’ use case collections map to more granular use cases outlined in the Open Research Information Agenda

¹⁴ <https://neo4j.com/licensing/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/UtrechtUniversity/ricgraph/blob/master/LICENSE>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/vivo-project/Vitro/blob/main/LICENSE>

¹⁷ <https://neo4j.com/developer/cypher/>

¹⁸ <https://graphacademy.neo4j.com/>

code. Costs to host the system on the SURF Research Cloud over the course of the pilot were negligible.¹⁹

6.5 Co-Collaboration, Co-Learning, and Co-Adaptation

A National PID Graph as outlined in this report will facilitate greater inter-organizational co-collaboration, co-learning, and co-adaptation. The multi-user central staging environment hosted on the Surf Research Cloud provides a boundary object within which researchers, research information specialists, and policy makers may work together with new forms of co-collaboration. For example, by combining self-validation activities of individual researchers with institutional-level data management processes to reduce rework.

Research information specialists across institutions could find new ways to co-collaborate with national policy makers and generate new forms of national-level research measures and ancillary services. Further co-collaboration between this and other ORIA pilot projects should provide additional value in facilitating this transition.

The use case roadmap outlined in Appendix F indicates a need to balance progress towards 'Open Information', 'Open Processes', and 'Open Organization'. Too little emphasis on any of these three dimensions may limit the realization of inter-organizational capabilities. As such, inter-organizational stakeholders must pilot and evaluate new combinations of use cases to (learn how to) reach an optimal inter-organizational configuration. Given this challenge, the proof-of-concept National PID Graph Architecture presents a unique opportunity to establish common goals that not only open research information and processes but also may facilitate co-learning between organizations.

Lastly, the graph analysis capabilities developed within the proof-of-concept National PID Graph Architecture may be further aligned with needs of broader initiatives. For example, by aligning capabilities of the proof-of-concept National PID Graph with developments within the European Graph Massivizer project²⁰ and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)²¹. The proof-of-concept architecture presents unique and strategically useful value in facilitating inter-organizational co-adaptation, thus accelerating the transition towards open science.²²

¹⁹ 200k Surf Research Cloud credits (~6600 Euros) were purchased during the pilot, as of 30/9/2023 70k were consumed (~2300 Euros). This provides a general indication of hosting costs. New estimate

²⁰ <https://graph-massivizer.eu/>

²¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

²² <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2023/03/29/open-science-nl-versnelt-transitie-naar-open-science>

7. Conclusion and Recommended Actions

In conclusion, the pilot has proven to be a valuable initiative for establishing a PID graph community. This community serves as a platform where one can gain insight into various perspectives of a PID graph, encompassing diverse values, information, qualities, and technologies.

We provide recommended actions towards the further development of a PID graph community and infrastructure that enables *national* reporting, analysis, assessment, evaluation, and dissemination currently not possible with existing research information systems.

The working group suggests a structural initiative is needed to further explore the value and technology of a PID graph and get endorsement from all research organizations and the community. That way we can work towards a ‘version of the truth’ presented by the National Graph to compare with ‘versions of the truth’ in complementary open research information sources. We recommend a detailed comparison of each open information source. For example, by comparing views on researcher-, organization-, and project- level productivity and impact within focused case studies of multi-stakeholder national research collaborations. This recommended approach would provide additional information on the quality and completeness of research information held in source CRIS systems and open research information systems, while at the same time further validating the efficacy of the Proof-of-Concept National PID Graph Architecture against major established alternatives.

In the following paragraphs, we enlist the recommendations per topic.

Community

To enhance our productivity and engagement with the community, we suggest implementing a more structured project approach, emphasizing a systematic method for addressing collective goals. Furthermore, we suggest establishing dedicated working groups where a specific user story or technology (e.g. AvantGraph) can be explored in expert groups.

To facilitate shared knowledge, we should keep investing in community building. Lastly, to strengthen our support network, we should promote a more robust support base within institutions, fostering collaboration and collective commitment to the success of our community initiatives.

- C1: More structured project approach
- C2: More focused activities (dedicated working groups on specific use cases and technology)
- C3: Shared knowledge through overview of state-of-the-art and literature (“startpagina”)
- C4: Promote support-base at institutions

Value and user stories

Many user stories were gathered and discussed over the course of the pilot and during the community events, but most lacked a concrete description of who it is for, what is specifically requested and what the value is. We therefore recommend better validation of a PID graph through more concrete user stories that include personas and derive requirements. In these user stories we need to address different values (reusability, accountability, quality, and digital sovereignty) and stakeholders (researcher, organization, project, funder, ...). The focus should lie on user stories that show added value at the national level, e.g., by analyzing and comparing collaboration networks.

In addition, we should involve umbrella organizations to verify why and under which conditions they want to contribute to a national portal. Involving these organizations more will help us to define more concrete user stories and gain support at the national level.

- V1: Better validation through more concrete user stories (who wants it, what is requested, what is the value). Include personas and derive requirements.
- V2: Involve umbrella organizations and verify why and under which conditions they want to contribute to a national portal

Information

A national PIDgraph can yield a wealth of information about research at a national scale. The PIDgraph proved particularly effective in detecting duplications within the combined CRIS data. However, the reusability of the data is an issue. In this pilot, we could only combine this data within a closed environment (SURF Research Cloud). Creating an open database from it is not possible without a very extensive privacy assessment (DPIA).

The decision to start with a minimal target schema such as the Research Graph Metamodel helped us to focus on the essential entities only. This schema also fits well with RicGraph, making it a strategic decision that prioritizes minimalism and vendor independence. However, there are essential distinctions between the target schema and the source schema (Pure-based). Certain entities (e.g. projects) are not fully covered in the target schema and it is therefore necessary to expand the schema in a follow-up project.

Additionally, comparing data from multiple sources (nationally and internationally) is challenging due to different terms and definitions, leading to various 'versions of the truth.' To address this issue, further investment is required to address.

Ultimately, the CRIS data can contribute to a national PID graph, creating a national "version of truth" that can be disseminated and enriched, where possible, with international databases such as OpenAlex and OpenAIRE.

- I1: Collaborative DPIA for researcher-records from institutional CRIS systems

- I2: Expand analysis to e.g. projects funders and grants (e.g. involve NWO) (e.g. via maDMP)
- I3: Based on user stories
 - Evaluate quality of sources
 - Evaluate “versions of truth”
- I4: Collaboration with metadata working group of Applied Science

Technology

The project team has explored the possibility to build a PID graph from scratch, which proved to be a complex endeavor. With limited technical capacity it was difficult to tackle challenges such DB optimizations and API management. For the next phase, it is advisable to engage existing experts, such as those from AvantGraph at TU Eindhoven.

- T1: Need for technical capacity (DB optimizations, API)
- Based on user stories
 - T2.1: Develop integration pipelines (FC4E technologies?)
 - T2.2: Develop user functionality such as researcher self-service portal
 - T2.3: And gradually “Integrate remaining UNL CRIS instantiations and other open research information sources within the proof-of-concept architecture”.
 - T2.4 Produce comparative benchmarks
- T3: Further explore lessons learned from other SKGs (OpenAire, Finland, Flanders, etc.)
- T4: Further analysis of open source solutions / software (e.g. Avantgraph technology by Eindhoven, used in SciLake, also FC4E metadata interoperability tools, Massivizer)

8. Appendices

Appendix A: Use Cases Extracted from the Open Research Information Agenda

1. Reporting: Being able to report on research as an individual, as an institution, and as umbrella organisations/country. Reports are carried out, among other things, for accountability to the subsidy provider, and for guidance (on impact). E.g. what your results of research have been; number of articles, % Open Access, up to (scientific and social) impact of your research. For this function, completeness and reliability of data is important.
2. Evaluate and assess: Evaluation is mainly formative assessment, and assessment is mainly summative assessment. Evaluate and assessment is done on individual (i.e. career development), research group (e.g. SEP), and Institution level. For this function, it is important that there is transparency about the information used for evaluation and assessment. In addition, there is a national (and European) movement to arrive at richer data. Qualitative data (eg narrative) are given greater importance in addition to the broader (social) impact (e.g. via altmetrics).
3. Analyze: Analytics provide insights to guide for example, priorities within the research landscape and the results of the research in the scholarly communication landscape. To increase these insights and other analysis possibilities a 'level playing field' for the use of the research information is important.
4. Archive, store and unlock: Archiving, storing and accessing is the management and retention of information in such a way that it is now and can also be used later for other purposes. This also includes making this information accessible and findable. Recently, more and more attention has been drawn to information about alternative outputs (such as data, software, learning materials, etc.), applying standards to this output (such as FAIR), open infrastructure, sustainable access and public governance.
5. Inform and disseminate: Informing the general public (companies, citizen scientists, politicians, journalists, etc.) about research in The Netherlands is a function to achieve 'societal engagement' and more social impact. Through research information such as who produces which research output, in collaboration with whom, and how if this is funded, citizens and businesses can access the information and possibly find a new application. This will increasingly shift from output at the end of the research chain to involvement earlier in the research chain. Furthermore, there will also be "products" that make it easier for social actors to use scientific knowledge in a usable/understandable way (from overlays to open education/open learning materials). This means that research information from more different research phases and more diverse research outputs will become available.

Appendix B: Concept Source and Destination Schemas

For more information, see: <https://researchgraph.org/schema/>

Appendix C: Complementary VIVO Functionality

The figure displays four screenshots of VIVO web application functionality:

- Top Left:** A page titled "What is VITRO?" explaining that Vitro is a general-purpose web-based ontology and instance editor. It lists capabilities such as creating/load ontologies, editing instances, building public web sites, and searching data. It includes a search bar and statistics for People (3.1k), Organizations (51), Research (57k), and Locations (323).
- Top Right:** A "Site Administration" page with sections for Data Input (including a dropdown for "Faculty Member (vivo)" and an "Add individual of this class" button), Site Configuration (with links like "Institutional internal class", "Manage profile editing", etc.), Ontology Editor (with links like "Ontology list", "Class Management", etc.), Property Management (with links like "Object property hierarchy", "Data property hierarchy", etc.), and Site Maintenance (with links like "Rebuild search index", "Rebuild visualization cache", etc.).
- Bottom Left:** An "Organizations" page showing a list of organizations with a search bar and a dropdown menu for "Organization (s)". The list includes "Advanced Research Center for Nanolithography (Netherlands)", "Amsterdam Neuroscience", "Association of universities in the Netherlands", "Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica", "Data Archiving and Networked Services", "Delft University of Technology", "Delta Institute for Theoretical Physics", and "Dutch Institute for Fundamental Energy Research".
- Bottom Right:** A Swagger API documentation page for "generate2vivo". It lists several endpoints for retrieving data from external sources like Crossref, DataCite Commons, ORCID, and ROR. Examples include:
 - `GET /crossref/personPublications`: Retrieve data about a person and their works from Crossref
 - `GET /crossref/works`: Retrieve data about a work from Crossref
 - `GET /datacitecommons/organization`: Retrieve organization data from DataCite Commons
 - `GET /datacitecommons/organizationPeople`: Retrieve data about an organization and its affiliated people from DataCite Commons
 - `GET /datacitecommons/person`: Retrieve data about a person from DataCite Commons
 - `GET /datacitecommons/personPublications`: Retrieve data about a person and their publications from DataCite Commons
 - `GET /datacitecommons/works`: Retrieve data about a work from DataCite Commons
 - `GET /orcid/currentEmployees`: Retrieve data about an organization's current employees and their works from ORCID
 - `GET /orcid/personPublications`: Retrieve data about a person and their works from ORCID
 - `GET /ror/organization`: Retrieve data about an organization from ROR
 - `GET /ror/organizationSubChildren`: Retrieve data about an organization and all their sub-organizations from ROR

For more information see: <https://github.com/vivo-community/generate2vivo>

Appendix D: Complementary Research in Context (Ric) Graph Functionality

Ricgraph explorer

[Home](#)
[Exact match search](#)
[String search](#)

You searched for:
 • value: "SURF"

Choose one node to continue:

name	category	value	comment	year	url_main	url_other	source	history
DOI	journal article	10.5194/esurf-5-617-2012	Effects of mud supply on large-scale estuary morphology and development over centuries to millennia	2012	url_main link		• OpenAlex-UU	▶ Click for history
DOI	journal article	10.5194/esurf-5-529-2012	The Usumacinta-Grijalva beach-ridge plain in southern Mexico: a high-resolution archive of river discharge and precipitation	2012	url_main link		• OpenAlex-LD • OpenAlex-TNO • OpenAlex-UU • OpenAlex-VU	▶ Click for history
DOI	journal article	10.5194/esurf-6-203-2018	Quantifying biostabilisation effects of biofilm-secreted and extracted extracellular polymeric substances (EPSs) on sandy substrate	2018	url_main link		• OpenAlex-UU	▶ Click for history
DOI	journal article	10.5194/esurf-6-187-2018	Establishing a sediment budget in the newly created "Oleie Noordwaard" wetland area in the Rhine-Meuse delta	2018	url_main link		• OpenAlex-UU	▶ Click for history
DOI	journal article	10.5194/esurf-5-731-2012	Turning the tide: comparison of tidal flow by periodic sea level fluctuation and by periodic bed tilting in scaled landscape experiments of estuaries	2012	url_main link		• OpenAlex-UU	▶ Click for history
DOI	working paper	10.5194/esurf-2017-11	Turning the tide: comparison of tidal flow by periodic sea level fluctuation and by periodic bed tilting in the Metronome tidal facility	2017	url_main link		• OpenAlex-UU	▶ Click for history
DOI	journal article	10.1016/j.cobsurf.2018.04.006	Virus reduction through microfiltration membranes modified with a cationic polymer for drinking water applications	2018	url_main link		• OpenAlex-UU	▶ Click for history

For more information see: <https://github.com/UtrechtUniversity/ricgraph>

Appendix E: Example data and subgraph visualizations

Figure 1: Example Subgraph Displaying Organization-Centric Network

Figure 2: Example Subgraph Displaying Publication-Centric Network

Figure 3: Example Subgraph Displaying Author-Centric Network

Figure 4: Meso-level view of Cross-Organizational ePID (doi) Subgraphs

Figure 5: Micro-level View of Cross-Organizational ePID (doi) Subgraphs

Figure 6: Matching NWO Products and Pure Publications by ePID

Figure 8: Meso-level view of NWO Project Clusters by NWO Funding Scheme

Appendix F: Preliminary Use Case Roadmap

R1 – Integration

- Complete overview of researcher output, complete set of identifiers for matching
- Showcase research information chain (from proposal to grant to project to result and reuse)
- Increase findability and reproducibility of research
- Downloadable integrated dataset so that researcher can easily reuse

R2 – Curation

- Enrich CRIS records (e.g. persons, publications)
- Get research output candidate records for internal persons (that do not have a formal source)
- Gain more impact and visibility for non peer reviewed items that do not have an import source
- Enrich master data (e.g. organizations, co-authors)
- Odd cases detector for amendment/enrichment

R3 - Generation

- Form and apply ontologies - inference
- Disambiguation (finding a specific value based on a set of identifying properties and relations)
- Normalization: match metadata elements from different sources - increase quality and trust
- Data model consensus e.g. relations between output and persons
- Complete set of properties and identifiers for master data
- Next generation impact tracking

R4 – Discovery

- National graph as middleware to transfer researcher records (profile, publications, cv)
- Reporting dashboarding on national level - national catalog
- Overview of all research outputs for an organization for evaluation or reporting
- Research topic-, activity-, funding- landscapes

Appendix G: Proof-of-Concept National PID Graph Architecture

The proof-of-concept **National PID Graph Architecture** provides a foundation to increase completeness and integrity of national research data following ORIA principles of openness, provenance, endurance, and sovereignty. The National PID Graph affords (sub) graph exports for use in complementary open research information research projects. Distilled subgraphs depict collaboration networks, degree networks, trend and gap analyses, organizational hierarchies, author and organization productivities, publication characteristics, and impact measures.

The Architecture contains three interacting layers (depicted in **Figure 1**) as follows:

Layer 1: which holds Pureroot node instances extracted from the Pure Authorships input file.

Layer 2: which holds a UNIQUE MESH of Abstracted Node Containers for Author, Publication, Organization and TLO nodes as well as all known relationships found during internal pattern matching. This layer establishes referential integrity by matching across unique identifiers.

Layer 3: which holds Internal/External Author, Internal/External Organization, and Publication node instances and properties sourced from input files.

Relevant between-node relationships are established via pattern matching algorithms.

Figure 1. Proof-of-Concept National PID Graph Architecture

Appendix H: User story validation (reporting)

Curating metadata in CRIS systems has become increasingly difficult in the last few years. The ongoing process of importing data from local source systems and publisher databases, and then re-integrating this data (often by hand) in local systems needs more advanced tooling to further automate and improve the process.

In general the workflows related to this process rely on matching and merging to keep the local research information database clean and up to date. Relational technology does this by finding matches in metadata based on a shared identifier (a DOI, or ORCID), to directly match records. Within a relational database we have to rely on the front end tooling provided by the software vendor, and matching identifiers to curate CRIS data effectively.

By aggregating CRIS data in a centralized graph, we gain a number of advantages to leverage curation workload. The focus of Graph technology on studying relationships in a network of data provides us with better tools to easily find relationships.

To showcase this, we loaded publication, staff and organization data from five Pure installations (Rotterdam, Groningen, Delft, Eindhoven and VU) for the years 2020-2023 using the API for each system. A simple way to find out if multiple Pure systems are curating the same data is to look at matching DOI's; if there are matches in DOI's in various systems we can conclude that there is a benefit to store curated records on a higher level, and distribute them to the systems where they are needed.

In a traditional database, we would need to write a script or index by iterating through the DOI's in one Pure system, and looking them up in the other Pure systems. In a graph, this can be improved vastly by a single query that describes the path between two CRIS systems that share a common DOI in that path.

Consider the following cypher query in Neo4j:

```
MATCH p=(o2:Organization {name:'TUE'})<-[:MANAGEDBY]-(pub2:Publication)-[:HAS_DOI]->(doi:Doi)<-[:HAS_DOI]-(pub:Publication)-[:MANAGEDBY]->(o:Organization {name:'TUD'})
RETURN p
```

This instantly shows us a visualization of the overlap in publications between TUE and TUD based on shared DOIs. Blue nodes are local publications connected to a local Pure system (red dot), pink dots are DOIs connected to the publications.

This is a fairly simple example relying on the presence of a DOI, but graph queries can also produce similar results by just analyzing relationships and/or the place of a node in a network. This allows us to find matching data not just on an identifier, but also by studying edges (relationships) in the graph. For instance if we find a publication node in one system without a DOI, but attached to a project node that is shared with another university, we might find a matching publication there (based on its place in the network) that does have a DOI, and infer that DOI to the original publication where it is missing.

A combination of graph technology and other smart tools (such as AI) can be combined to construct and enrich a national graph of research. This graph can be used to:

- study collaboration in a nontraditional way (i.e. not just co-authorships) by examining edge networks in the graph.
- share curation; through uploading curated metadata from local CRIS systems to a national graph, the graph can function as a centralized shared source of qualitative metadata that can be used to match and download data to local systems, leveraging the workload of CRIS administrators.
- integrating local data into a national graph, through which local systems can benefit from the larger network in terms of analyzing relationships such as collaborations and impact
- infer missing data in the national graph to automate enrichment of metadata (benefitting shared curation and further insights).